

Table 1. Growth characteristics of new plant type lines compared with those of high-yielding cultivars. Yawara, Japan. 1994.

Cultivar/line	Days to heading ^a (no.)	Biological yield ^b (g m ⁻²)	SD ^c	Specific leaf area ^d (cm ² g ⁻¹)	Leaf area index ^d	Panicle number (no. m ⁻¹)	Spikelet number (no. panicle ⁻¹)	LB/TDW ^e	NSC ^f content (%)	ADWr ^g (g m ⁻²)	Lodging score ^h
<i>May transplanting</i>											
IR65598-112-2	89	1737	146	185	7.2	144	367	0.33	39.1	392	0
IR66740-AC1-3	92	1605	344	180	9.0	317	131	0.37	31.8	150	0
Kochihibiki	77	1539	104	217	6.5	499	70	0.30	10.5	474	3.2
Takanari	82	2006	65	206	7.0	281	182	0.28	10.8	786	0
IR36	85	1800	60	232	6.6	580	88	0.27	6.8	645	4
IR72	88	1753	137	212	8.2	501	109	0.32	4.7	458	3.5
<i>June transplanting</i>											
IR65598-112-2	76	1494	2	159	4.6	118	326	0.29	13.8	444	0
IR66740-AC1-3	85	1625	139	171	7.5	217	171	0.36	34.9	305	0
Kochihibiki	69	1575	54	208	6.7	399	83	0.32	4.4	505	3.3
Takanari	73	1869	25	208	7.3	239	200	0.30	8.9	619	0.5
IR36	77	1654	35	228	6.2	445	101	0.26	5.1	504	4
IR72	77	1698	122	182	6.0	395	122	0.29	8.7	498	4

^aCounted from transplanting. ^bAll data are shown on a dry weight basis. ^cSD= standard deviation. ^dMeasured at heading stage. ^ePartitioning ratio of dry weight to leaf blade. ^fNonstructural carbohydrate content in culm at maturity. ^gDry weight increase during ripening phase. ^hScored on a 0-4 scale where 0 = no lodging and 4 = hardly lodged.

Table 2. Economic yield and yield components of new plant type lines. Tsukuba, Japan. 1994.

Cultivar/line	Spikelet number (no. m ⁻²)	Grain fill ^a (%)	Grain weight ^b (g m ⁻²)	Sink size ^{b,c} (g m ⁻²)	Economic yield ^b (g m ⁻²)	SD ^d	Harvest index ^e
<i>May transplanting</i>							
IR65598-112-2	528	44.9	20.9	1104	495	48	0.25
IR66740-AC1-3	414	37.2	23.3	965	359	78	0.20
Kochihibiki	347	71.1	23.1	802	570	16	0.32
Takanari	511	88.5	21.5	1099	972	19	0.42
IR36	513	80	19.8	1016	813	15	0.39
IR72	547	62	20.0	952	590	52	0.34
<i>June transplanting</i>							
IR65598-112-2	385	49.7	22.3	859	427	7	0.25
IR66740-AC1-3	372	36.6	24.1	897	328	28	0.18
Kochihibiki	330	81	24.1	795	644	61	0.36
Takanari	479	83.4	20.9	1001	835	28	0.39
IR36	451	84.5	19.7	888	751	16	0.39
IR72	482	72.4	20.8	1003	726	41	0.37

^aPercentage of grains that sunk in water total spikelet⁻¹. ^bShown on a brown rice basis at 15% moisture content. The multiplication of grain or kernel weight and spikelet number m⁻². ^cSD = standard deviation. ^eHarvest index = brown rice yield/biological yield.

inactivated along with the wider variation in the weight of fertilized kernels and increased nonstructural carbohydrate content in the culm at maturity (Table 1).

Another factor was less dry weight increase during ripening, characterized by a higher dry weight at heading due to the larger partitioning of dry weight to leaves, especially in IR66740-ACI-3.

These results indicate that panicle weight type rice may not always be high-yielding unless accompanied by an effective grain sink. Less inactivation of the grain sink of NPT lines would ensure a yield level similar to that of IR72. For further increase in potential yield, a higher biological yield—similar to that of Takanari—will be essential. □

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Breaking seed dormancy in different leguminous forage species

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Clitoria (*Clitoria ternatea* L.), *crotalaria* (*Crotalaria juncea* L.), *siratro* (*Macropodium atripurpureum* [DC] Urb.), and

desmanthus (*Desmanthus virgatus* (L.) Willd) have potential as leguminous green manures for rainfed lowland fields after the main rice crop in the Philippines. But their thick, hard seed coverings can cause problems for germination. To break seed dormancy, we subjected the seeds to a treatment of H₂SO₄ (commercial grade, 96%) for 15 min and to scrubbing for 15 min with sand, using mild force. The experiment was replicated three times.

Seed germination was 98.0% for *clitoria* and 95.3% for *siratro* with the H₂SO₄ treatment, which was considerably higher than sand scrubbing and for the control

(Table 1). In *crotalaria*, seed germination was 99.3% without any treatment, 97.3% with sand, and 89.3% with H₂SO₄. *Desmanthus* did not respond well to any of the treatments; the highest germination was 17.3% with sand scrubbing. The seeds did not survive the H₂SO₄ treatment.

To improve the germination of *desmanthus*, we conducted another experiment using various treatments (Table 2). Treating the seeds with H₂SO₄ for 8 min increased the germination to 87.3%. The seeds must be washed very quickly after treatment to prevent them from being subjected to a temperature of more than

Table 1. Seed germination (% after 192 h) of leguminous species under different treatments.^a

Treatment	Clitoria	Crotalaria	Siratro	Desmanthus	Mean
H ₂ SO ₄ (concentrated) for 15 min	98.0	89.3	95.3	0.0	70.7 a
Scrubbing with sand for 15 min	55.3	97.3	18.0	17.3	47.0 b
Control	49.3	99.3	16.7	16.0	45.3 b
Mean	67.6 b	95.3 a	43.3 c	11.1 d	

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

45°C. A more practical treatment of soaking the seeds in hot water for 15 min gave seed germination of 68.0%. Dry cold and wet cold treatments were not effective. The boiling water treatment damaged the seeds and resulted in no germination.

The hot water (65 °C) treatment for 15 min also improved the germination of

siratro, with a germination rate of 39% after 192 h. Clitoria, however, did not respond and germination was only 2%.

In conclusion, crotalaria seeds do not require any breaking of dormancy to germinate. Applying concentrated H₂SO₄ for 15 min was most effective in breaking dormancy in clitoria and siratro. For

Table 2. Germination of desmanthus seeds under different treatments.^a

Treatment	Germination rate (% after 192 h)
Dry cold at 2 °C for 24 h	16.7 d
Wet cold at 2 °C for 24 h	14.0 d
Boiling water for 15 min	00.0 e
Hot water at 65 °C for 15 min	68.0 b
H ₂ SO ₄ (concentrated for 8 min)	87.3 a
Control	23.3 c

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

desmanthus, a shorter treatment time (8 min) with concentrated H₂SO₄ is recommended. Where high germination rate is not critical and H₂SO₄ availability may be a problem, treating desmanthus and siratro with hot water (65 °C) for 15 min is suggested. ■

Fertilizer management— inorganic sources

Responses of promising rice genotypes to nitrogen levels in irrigated lowlands

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Lowlands in Bihar constitute about 2.2 million ha, which is about 42% of the total rice area. Rice varieties selected for their nutrient requirements—particularly for N—have great relevance for boosting overall production of lowland rice in Bihar.

The performances of genotypes IET 5760, IET 5914, and IET 8002 were evaluated against national check Pankaj and local checks Radha and Rajshree at five N levels (0, 40, 80, 120, and 160 kg ha⁻¹).

The soil was silt loam in texture, with a pH of 8.6, 0.46% organic C, and 213 kg available N ha⁻¹, 8.4 kg available P ha⁻¹, and 73 kg available K ha⁻¹. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with the genotypes in the main plot and N in the subplots.

Thirty-day-old seedlings of different genotypes were transplanted during the last week of July. The recommended doses of 17.6 kg P ha⁻¹ and 16.6 kg K ha⁻¹, along with one-fourth of the N according to the

Interaction effect of N application and genotype on grain yield (t ha⁻¹), N uptake (kg ha⁻¹), and net return (US\$ ha⁻¹).^a

Rice genotype	N levels (kg ha ⁻¹)											
	0		40		80		120		160		Average	
IET5760	1.06	[17.4]	2.04	[41.8]	2.73	[60.3]	3.04	[68.5]	3.08	[70.3]	2.39	[51.7]
	(-88.8)		(58.1)		(101.6)		(130.4)		(125.9)		(65.4)	
IET5914	2.26	[38.7]	3.29	[68.5]	4.06	[88.6]	4.46	[101.1]	4.56	[106.5]	3.73	[80.7]
	(60.6)		(201.15)		(261.5)		(301.7)		(306.2)		(226.2)	
IET8002	3.30	[58.3]	4.42	[91.3]	4.97	[108.6]	5.45	[121.2]	5.74	[114.8]	4.78	[98.8]
	(188.4)		(347.1)		(372.50)		(420.7)		(412.2)		(348.1)	
Rajshree	3.39	[60.6]	4.44	[93.3]	5.04	[112.7]	5.12	[116.1]	5.09	[114.2]	4.62	[99.4]
	(195.7)		(353.5)		(384.6)		(384.8)		(371.6)		(338.1)	
Radha	2.44	[40.4]	3.28	[73.6]	4.17	[93.1]	4.98	[113.2]	5.46	[124.4]	4.07	[88.9]
	(85.5)		(212.8)		(279.3)		(367.90)		(414.3)		(272)	
Pankaj	2.39	[41.8]	3.39	[67.5]	4.44	[86.9]	5.24	[114.2]	5.36	[118.6]	4.17	[85.8]
	(79.2)		(220.8)		(293.2)		(394.1)		(395)		(276.4)	
Av	2.47	[42.9]	3.48	[72.7]	4.23	[91.7]	4.72	[105.7]	4.88	[108.1]	-	
	(86.8)		(232.2)		(282.1)		(333.3)		(337.5)			
					Grain yield		N uptake		Net return			
LSD (0.05)	For subplot treatment at the same level of main plot treatment				0.30		8.2		1009			
	For main plot treatment at the same level of subplot treatment				0.31		8.3		1087			

^aValues in [] indicate N uptake and in (), net return. ^bMain plot treatment is variety, and subplot treatment is N level.